

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ENERGY RISKS ASSESSMENT AND RESILIENT STRATEGIES DEVELOPMENT CONSIDERING THE WAR IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

This article analyses the risks to energy supply during the war in Ukraine for developing diversification strategies under extreme conditions. The analysis focuses on the challenges, including infrastructure damage, power capacity destruction, supply chain disruptions, and the volatility of conventional energy options as grid power and fossil fuels. The risks to energy security were analysed using the PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors) framework, structured under risk definition, risk evaluation, and risk mitigation for each factor. By diversifying energy sources, improving renewable energy, decentralising control through microgrids, investing in energy storage, hardening infrastructure, enhancing energy efficiency, prioritising cybersecurity, and fostering community resilience, countries can better protect their citizens from the impacts of energy disruptions. A Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) approach was used to calculate a comparative assessment of technical energy supply solutions. Three types of scenarios for the development of Ukraine's energy security were developed based on risk assessment, analysis of energy resilience strategies, and a review of successful technical solutions for energy supply in crisis conditions. Ukraine's experience could be helpful for energy strategies of other countries facing increasing threats of war, aggression, terrorist attacks, and climate change.

Keywords: war in Ukraine, energy safety, risk assessment, predicted scenario, energy strategy.

Introduction.

Ongoing massive attacks on Ukraine's energy infrastructure have destroyed electricity generation and distribution facilities, caused massive outages, and significantly increased the risk of widespread blackouts. Shelling of the Ukrainian power system are systematic, focusing on the transmission system, electricity network, the conventional power plants, mainly on substations and thermal and hydro generation. Since the beginning of the invasion, Russia has attacked over 200 Ukrainian energy facilities. Some facilities have been hit more than 40 times, and no region has escaped attacks [14]. Targeted massive attacks on energy infrastructure and facilities in 20 regions destroyed 50% of electricity generation and 54% of the facilities, but actual losses are higher, as 4.8 GW were restored or built in this period [17]. Ukraine has lost more than two thirds of energy potential, compared to the electricity capacity before the war [7]. The total cost of Ukraine recovery as of December 31, 2024, is \$486 billion, and this amount is growing with each passing day of the war [13].

Currently, the level of general danger is increasing worldwide due to the spread of political-military tensions, terrorist threats and the increase in extreme weather events due to climate change. All these threats increase the risks of destabilisation of energy supply. The events of April 28, 2025, when Spain, Portugal, Andorra and part of France were plunged into darkness after a large-scale blackout, show that developed European countries are not ready for energy destabilization. During the war, Ukraine faces numerous challenges,

and the experience of overcoming them can be useful to other countries in preparing for various crisis situations. The analysis will allow not only Ukraine but also other states to avoid wrong steps in the future. It is important to identify all critical points and risk areas for proper strategic planning of the development of the energy sector.

Thus, the purpose of this study is to analyse the risks to energy supply in extreme conditions and develop strategies for their diversification, using the example of Ukraine's war experience. In accordance with this goal, the following tasks have been formulated:

- 1) explore the urgent challenges and risks for Ukraine's energy infrastructure, which endures recurrent power disruptions due to continuous attacks;
- 2) analyse possible ways to diversify energy supply risks in extreme conditions based on the Ukrainian experience;
- 3) develop scenarios for the formation of a sustainable energy system in the face of increasing threats of military aggression, terrorist attacks, and extreme weather events due to climate change.

Methodology.

This study used an analytical framework PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal) to systematically classify and evaluate the multidimensional risks influencing Ukraine's energy security. Each dimension is decomposed into a set of key risk indicators and structured under risk definition, risk evaluation, and risk mitigation. for each factor. The framework aims to determine the relative

weight and interdependencies among these categories to support strategic decision-making.

This research methodology is based on a thorough analysis of data with verification to ensure accuracy and reliability of the results. The quality and correctness of the information reflect the actual scale of the impact of war on Ukraine's energy security. Digital data were derived from research and open official statistics by next category: 1) government ministries of Ukraine – Ministry of Energy of Ukraine, Ministry of Health of Ukraine, Ministry of Environmental Protection and Natural Resources of Ukraine, Ministry for Communities, Territories and Infrastructure Development of Ukraine; 2) government agencies and regulatory authorities – National Commission for State Regulation of Energy and Public Utilities of Ukraine, State Statistics Service of Ukraine; 3) state-owned enterprises – National power company "Ukrenergo", public joint stock company "Ukrhydroenergo"; 4) Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) – Dixi Group (Ukrainian think tank focused on energy sector transparency and reform), Ecoaction – centre for environmental initiatives, Initiative on greenhouse gas accounting of war; 5) private sector entities – DTEK (Donbas Fuel and Energy Company), Top Lead (strategic content and data communication agency); 6) academic and research institutions and associations – Kyiv School of Economics (KSE), Energy Map (Ukrainian energy analytics platform), Bioenergy association of Ukraine; 7) international organizations – the World Bank, the European Commission, UNDP (United Nations Development Programme), OSCE (Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe), the Energy Community Secretariat.

Algorithms k-means clustering and principal component analysis identify structural relationships and data groupings. Correlation matrix construction and network analysis visualize the strength and direction of inter-factor relationships. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method determines the rank of the factors that are part of a system by weighting them pairwise. A structured scoring and normalization method based on frequency, emphasis, and criticality of each risk provide a mathematical justification for the approximate weights assigned to Ukrainian energy safety risks.

Each risk frequency and emphasis analyzed by scoring scale from 1 to 5 and to turn the scores into percentage weights this formula used:

$$\text{Weight}_i = (\text{Score}_i / \sum_{i=1} \text{Score}_i) \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

These weights were mathematically derived using a scoring system based on qualitative importance normalized to give a fair and proportional risk distribution. This method ensures clarity, reproducibility, and transparency of the risk evaluation.

The weights of each PESTEL dimension were normalized on a scale from 0 to 1 to enable comparative analysis. The risk of model bias mitigated by validation assessment of energy and environmental expertise to confirm and refine AI-derived weights. To explore potential future developments, scenario modelling was applied to assess how different intensities of war-related disruptions, climate conditions, and regulatory alignment with the EU could impact Ukraine's energy

security. Each scenario incorporates the weighted PESTEL factors and simulates their influence under dynamic conditions. While AI enhances the reliability of risk weighting, the methodology is constrained by data availability and the rapidly evolving geopolitical environment. Since Ukraine does not control part of the territory and active hostilities are taking place on its territory, it is only sometimes possible to obtain complete, reliable, and up-to-date data from the occupied area. This data may change significantly as Ukraine liberates new territory and government agencies and experts gain more information.

Main part.

Historically, Ukraine's power system was designed to accommodate significantly higher consumption levels and electricity transmission in multiple directions. This architecture provided redundancy and reserve capacity, which helped the system partially withstand large-scale damage from Russian attacks. However, current challenges demand a rethinking of system management approaches, including the implementation of bidirectional electricity trading with EU member states, decentralization of generation assets, and the integration of variable renewable energy sources [15].

Since 2017, Ukraine had planned synchronization with the European Network of Transmission System Operators (ENTSO-E), initially scheduled for 2023. On the very day of the full-scale invasion, the country conducted a planned test of operating in isolated mode by disconnecting from the Russian and Belarusian grids. Following the invasion, Ukraine and Moldova requested emergency synchronization, which was completed in record time—in just a few weeks. Electricity trade commenced in June 2022, with gradual increases in trading limits. As of now, the maximum trade capacity from continental Europe to Ukraine and Moldova stands at 1.7 GW, additionally supported by an inter-Transmission System Operator (TSO) emergency agreement that enables several hundred megawatts of short-term support under suitable grid conditions [13].

Prior to 2022, nuclear power accounted for half of Ukraine's electricity production, followed by coal-fired thermal power plants at 23% and gas-fired plants at 9% [20]. According to the State Statistics Service, more than one-third of Ukrainian households were connected to district heating systems. Approximately 70% of thermal energy was produced using natural gas, with around one-third generated by combined heat and power plants (CHPs), and the remainder by conventional boilers and other sources [16].

Due to Russia's destruction of the Ukrainian energy system, Ukraine had to rely heavily on imported electricity in 2024, when the import was record-high 4.1 TWh of electricity in 2024, five times the amount in 2023. Imports in late 2024 fell largely due to high prices in neighbouring countries and price caps on the domestic spot market, thereby worsening power shortages [4].

A comprehensive evaluation of the damage, losses, and recovery needs within Ukraine's energy sector resulting from the full-scale invasion by the Russian Federation is presented in Fig. 1. The data is based

on data from the Kyiv School of Economics, the Ministry of Energy of Ukraine, and the Ministry for Communities, Territories and Infrastructure Development of Ukraine [9].

Fig. 1. An assessment of Ukrainian energy system destruction caused by the war based on data from the Kyiv school of economics: (a) Energy sector of Ukraine, (b) Oil and gas, (c) Electric power industry, and (d) Power generation.

Findings.

The global world order has changed since the end of the era of globalisation, which will lead to a number of irreversible shifts in all spheres of human life. The ongoing war in Ukraine has severely impacted the country's energy infrastructure, caused widespread blackouts, and increased the risk of energy supply disruptions. A PESTEL-based analysis of energy security risks in Ukraine during wartime defines risks, evaluates their impact, and identifies ways for risk mitigation. This comprehensive analysis aims to inform strategic planning and policy development to enhance Ukraine's energy resilience amid ongoing challenges.

Political risks.

Global changes are taking place in diplomacy, relations between countries, and in the foreign policy of states in general. Relations between allies are breaking down, old military alliances are collapsing, while the militarisation of individual countries is increasing, which increases instability and uncertainty. The main geopolitical challenges for all countries in the world today are shifting global centers of economic and trade power, especially changes in the allocation and delivery of energy supplies. Given the ongoing war and geopolitical tensions, as well as historical precedents, the risk

of manipulation of energy flows remains substantial. Political and legislative changes may cause rising costs associated with greenhouse gas emissions, stricter reporting requirements, and expanded regulatory measures governing existing products, manufacturing processes, and services.

For Ukraine, the main political challenge related to energy security is the aggressive war started by Russia, so Ukraine's policy space is seriously constrained due to the war (Fig. 2). Targeted attacks by the aggressor on the energy framework, encompassing power generation facilities, transmission networks, and gas distribution pipelines, lead to catastrophic impacts such as widespread blackouts, heating failures, and critical infrastructure shutdowns. Severe impact disruptions can lead to energy shortages and economic losses; therefore, it is necessary to harden infrastructure, strengthen physical security measures, and maintain strategic energy reserves. Infrastructure and physical measures mean reinforcing substations and pipelines, deploying rapid-repair mobile substations, and developing decentralised energy systems, microgrids, and on-site generation.

Fig. 2. Analytic assessment of political risk for Ukrainian energy security by hierarchy, %.

Economical risks

Global political changes have led to the end of economic globalisation, which creates multiple threats to supply chains and logistics (Fig. 3). As a result of the completion of globalisation, the production cycle may be completely closed within states or separate eco-

nomical unions. Global markets react to war by reformatting global economic influences with significant implications for the energy sector. Disruption of energy markets causes price volatility, currency depreciation, inflation, and a deficit of capital investments. The disruption of the logistical routes of world trade may become the cause of a global financial crisis.

Fig. 3. Analytic assessment of economic risk for Ukrainian energy security by hierarchy, %.

In Ukraine, war-dependent economic development leads to changes in the economic environment and energy sector. Problems arise with imports for repairs and maintenance of energy infrastructure, and there are complications in procuring spare parts. Dependence on imports and funding shortages inhibits the development of energy infrastructure. Leveraging international aid helps a lot to support the energy sector, in particular to build national stockpiles of diesel, gas, and critical spare parts.

Long-term functionality and sustainability of the electricity system require significant investments and reforms. Key priorities include the establishment of a national emissions trading system, enhanced financial support from the European Union, and improvements in transparency and strategic governance. However, investment attractiveness remains low due to several inhibiting factors: an inadequate regulatory environment, ongoing wartime risks, uncertainty surrounding the future configuration of the power system, and elevated capital costs [20]. The opacity of the energy market lies at the root of the low investment attractiveness of the energy sector. The influence of big financial groups, monopolies, and a lack of competition restrictions are blocking the transition to new models of energy organisation. A lack of financial resources and a decline in disposable income of consumers and businesses lead to debt and a non-payment crisis. This situation has produced a self-reinforcing negative feedback loop: limited investor confidence in future market revenues results in higher risk premiums, thereby inflating the cost of capital. Consequently, investment in energy infrastructure is only viable when electricity can be sold at

prohibitively high prices to Ukrainian consumers [7]. According to the forecast of the Ukraine Macroeconomic Handbook, stabilisation of the cost of electricity is one of the main drivers of slowing inflation by mid-2025 [9]. To mobilize investment in targeted, systemic solutions, it is essential to empower local and private actors through integrated mechanisms. These may include war-risk insurance, export credit guarantees, structured project financing, streamlined access to land and grid infrastructure, and the identification of viable off-takers within Ukraine. Although resolving these systemic barriers is complex, providing investors with guaranteed minimum revenue levels for low-carbon technologies could meaningfully enhance investment incentives.

Disruptions in the regular operations of critical infrastructure and large-scale damage to industrial facilities can have serious environmental consequences. Climate change exacerbates these problems, which in turn can exacerbate emergencies and environmental disasters, putting additional pressure on local communities. For the mitigation of energy risks, there is a need for transparency of the energy market, diversification of energy import sources from allied nations, investment in domestic energy production capabilities, and the stockpiling of strategic reserves. The formation of new energy markets should be based on ESG (environment, social, governance) principles that ensure transparency of supply chains, compliance with environmental standards, and the social responsibility of business.

Russian attacks on critical infrastructure are a persistent challenge for the country's energy system. Among the 1,433 industrial and infrastructure facilities

affected by the hostilities, 50 are part of the energy sector [13]. Losses from the destruction until February 2023 include 1,344 critical infrastructure facilities, 27.2 extractives sites, 38 power generation facilities, 9 nuclear facilities and 3.1 million tons of oil and petroleum products burned [17]. Naftogaz has recovered approximately half of the gas production capacity that it lost in attacks, but storage levels nonetheless remain concerningly low. Additional destruction to the energy infrastructure would have a noticeable impact on the recovery of Ukraine's economy, because the energy sectors are critical enablers for growth in all other spheres. Frequent power outages and fuel shortages raise costs for manufacturers, making investments in logistics and energy sectors important factors in unleashing the sectors' potential. Despite the deceleration, the economy continues to demonstrate remarkable resilience in the face of persistent attacks on critical infrastructure, including energy facilities [9].

Social risks

Targeted and regular attacks by the enemy on Ukrainian energy facilities are leading to a humanitarian crisis. Only during one aerial attack on 26 August 2024, Russia launched over 200 missiles and drones targeting Ukraine's energy infrastructure. As a result, approximately 8 million households experienced power outages. In addition to the risk of being killed due to fighting, war creates many health problems (Fig. 4). Risks to the life and health of the population are increasing due to the lack of energy supply in houses and critical infrastructure. During winter, as temperatures fall below freezing, electricity demand peaks, resulting in a power shortfall of 5.8 GW – almost equivalent to the capacity of the occupied Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant [13]. Mortality and morbidity increase in winter due to heating outages and in summer due to lack of air conditioning, especially among vulnerable groups of the population, and in other seasons due to lack of energy for water supply and cooking fuels.

Fig. 4. Analytic assessment of social risk for Ukrainian energy security by hierarchy, %.

Russian shelling of Ukrainian fuel storage facilities releases pollutants that harm the air, environment, and population. The estimated total number of attacks on fuel storage facilities during the war is 91 units, of which 46 are oil depots, 20 are storage facilities, 10 are gas stations, 8 are plants, and 7 are other objects. In general, damage to the atmospheric air caused by the full-scale war up to the end of 2024 is assessed at 17.7 bln USD, of which 3.4 bln USD is damage to the air quality caused by the burning of oil, oil products, and gas [14]. As a result of attacks on an oil depot, 3.1 mln tons of oil and oil products burned down, and the concentration of harmful substances in the air after each strike on an oil depot increased 10.1 times for Chlorine and 2.1 times for Hydrochloric acid. The mortality rate from air pollution annually increases per 100K people – 79 in Ukraine and 45 in Poland [17].

War also harms people through contact with harmful substances, inhalation of gases, soil and water pollution, and destruction of the environment. Large-scale destruction of energy and water facilities essential for supplying, purifying, and retaining water leaves people without access to clean drinking water, heightening the risk of an environmental and humanitarian catastrophe. Fifteen percent of women and fourteen percent of men in Ukraine do not have access to clean drinking water due to the war [14]. The consequences of environmental pollution due to a full-scale war will be felt for years by people and nature, from water pollution to mental health.

The population is displaced from the territories with a destroyed power system that cannot be repaired

due to the constant threat of shelling. As a result of the war, the population is declining, migration is increasing, living standards are getting worse, and energy consumer and employment patterns are changing. The 20% decline in residential energy consumption is primarily attributed to the departure of 6.5 million Ukrainian refugees, though various policies and initiatives have contributed to electricity conservation [4]. Communication with transparent, real-time information on outages and restoration schedules was implemented. Load shedding and rolling blackouts have become common as utilities ration scarce energy supplies. For fair and predictable energy distribution, coordinated outage schedules were introduced. Public shelters (invincibility posts) equipped with uninterrupted energy supply have been created in cities. For vulnerable populations, subsidies and assistance programs are provided. Local communities have made significant progress in achieving energy autonomy through a decentralization reform implemented after 2014, granting local authorities the financial autonomy and legal authority necessary to tackle local challenges [20]. Numerous households and businesses have acquired compact diesel generators and power banks as contingency measures to sustain electricity supply during outages. Autonomous energy supply technologies and energy storage devices have been used to socially protect the population of Ukraine from energy-related humanitarian threats.

The lack of energy reduces labor productivity and income opportunities for people, which affects human rights and labor standards. The physically capable male workforce, many possessing expertise in infrastructure

development, is predominantly involved in combat or granted exemptions to fulfil other critical national duties [8]. The personnel have to work in emergency situations under the threat of repeated shelling, so the training system and procedures need to be improved to increase security. In the energy labor market with human resource shortage, more jobs are being filled by women, replacing men who have gone to war or been killed in the process of repairing the destroyed energy infrastructure.

Ukraine's labor market remains fundamentally imbalanced due to the prolonged impact of the full-scale war, which has led to mobilization and significant outmigration. The unemployment rate in Ukraine is projected to continue on its downward trajectory, reflecting a gradual labor market recovery. However, structural labor market challenges persist, including skills mismatches and difficulties in sourcing qualified

labor. These labor market frictions could weigh on economic growth prospects, underscoring the need for targeted policies to address the skill mismatch and enhance workforce participation in different categories, including veterans [9].

Technological risks

Targeted attacks on Ukrainian energy network led to the destruction of power plants, transmission lines, substations, and gas pipelines. Energy infrastructure deterioration exceeds 50% for electrical networks and reaches 70% for individual facilities [7]. Repair is complicated by logistic and personnel shortages necessary for maintenance, repair, and operation of bombed and outdated energy systems. War limits access to critical equipment and technology, and regulatory ambiguity under martial law complicates logistics and procurement (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Analytic assessment of technological risk for Ukrainian energy security by hierarchy, %.

Ukraine's impaired energy production capacity must be rehabilitated to the fullest extent feasible by upgrading transmission lines, and it also needs to quickly increase import capability, and establish new generation capacities. Currently, most of Ukrenergo's first-tier energy infrastructure facilities are already 85% protected. Energoatom facilities are protected by appropriate air defence means. Ukraine protects energy facilities with the first and second levels of protection. The first level of protection consists of gabions with sand. The second consists of reinforced concrete powerful structures that can withstand direct drone strikes and also protect energy facilities from missile debris [13].

Just before the full-scale invasion of Ukraine, the enemy carried out a massive cyberattack on state administration and life support systems. Cyberattacks continue throughout the war, including on energy infrastructure, threatening widespread service disruptions, loss of data, and control. For cybersecurity hardening, it is necessary to upgrade protocols, maintain override redundancy procedures, and stockpile analogue control equipment. The legacy grid components need to be replaced with smart, resilient devices. Significant capacity losses emphasize the need to accelerate the advancing decentralized energy production, including renewable energy sources and flexible capacities, and increase their share in the energy balance. Reconstruction needs new energy-efficient technologies by deploying adaptable and distributed energy production systems, encompassing cogeneration and renewable sources.

While the initial investment in renewable energy systems and battery storage may be higher, the long-term benefits of energy security and independence make diversification a crucial strategy for mitigating

the risks of war-related energy disruptions. Localized generation using renewables offers a reliable source of power during grid outages and enhances resilience, though the deployment of technologies such as heat pumps, wind turbines, and solar photovoltaics (PV) in dense urban areas is constrained by specific technical and operational limitations. As of early 2024, consumer-installed solar PV systems accounted for nearly 1,500 MW of capacity, with deployment trends showing consistent growth [11]. While installing PV systems on multi-storey buildings does not fully address wintertime energy needs – given that panel efficiency may drop to as low as 10% – such systems can still partially meet energy demands during summertime power outages [4].

To enhance grid stability under extreme wartime conditions, localized implementation of dispatchable gas-fired generation is advisable. This includes integrating balancing technologies with a wide regulatory range for various loads and deploying peaker plants for emergency response. In response to these needs, the Ukrainian government has promoted the use of decentralised generation – especially the deployment of small modular gas turbines with capacities between 5 and 40 MW – and encouraged the rapid installation of rooftop solar with battery storage across critical infrastructure, such as public institutions, healthcare facilities, educational institutions, residential buildings, and commercial enterprises [14]. An integrated approach – combining centralized supply, renewable generation, peaker plants, and balancing technologies – is only feasible with the support of robust energy storage systems. These systems are vital for maintaining supply reliability and enabling dynamic energy management.

Decentralisation of power generation, alongside enhancements in balancing capacity, is essential to improve the operational flexibility of Ukraine's electric power system—that is, its ability to meet real-time demand fluctuations. Energy development plans must take into account the urgent needs of energy supply in wartime conditions and at the same time the long-term prospects for post-war reconstruction. In crisis situations, the need increases for decentralised and diversified energy solutions that reduce reliance on vulnerable, centralised systems and enhance resilience. For demand management, off-peak consumption is incentivised, and energy efficiency programs are implemented to reduce overall demand. Advanced demand-side management technologies equipped with intelligent control systems enable optimal energy utilization, mitigate peak load stress, reduce electricity expenditures, and improve both energy security and supply reliability. Significant investments in upgrading modernisation and regular maintenance of energy systems are needed to reduce technological risks.

Environmental risks

As a result of the destruction of power plants and shelling of energy structures during the war, it does not only kill people but also cause catastrophic damage to the environment (Fig. 6). This is long-term contamination that takes years to clean up, with catastrophic environmental consequences for ecosystems. Damaged and destroyed infrastructure significantly pollutes the environment and leaves behind economic and social consequences, severely threatening the environment

and public health. Chemicals and toxic substances from the damaged industry subsequently spread through the air and into the ground and water, involving animals, plants, and people. More than 175 mln tons CO₂-eq greenhouse gas emissions have been caused by the full-scale war, including 17.2 mln tons of CO₂-eq due to the energy infrastructure. The assessment of environmental damage caused by hostilities reached 62.9 bln USD by the middle of September 2024 [17].

One day of full-scale war causes 4 billion UAH of damage to the environment, and this is without taking into account the ecocide at the Kakhovka hydroelectric power plant (HPP). Thus, as a result of the explosion of the Kakhovka HPP, people and animals died, the landscape and vegetation completely changed, and ecosystem succession occurred. The explosion of the Kakhovka HPP dam caused lasting environmental damage where the washed-away garbage volume is estimated at 2.9 mln m³ [17]. The wave from the reservoir flooded 54 unsafe facilities that could be sources of pollution, including chemical and pharmaceutical plants, oil depots, and water treatment plants. The norm for the concentration of petroleum products was exceeded by 6.6 times in the Black Sea after the destruction of the Kakhovka HPP dam. More than 49 mines in the Donbas region are flooded and will no longer be able to operate. The occupation of the Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Power Plant increased the threat of a nuclear accident to the maximum, which creates the danger of radioactive contamination not only of the regions of Ukraine but also of the territories of neighbouring countries.

Fig. 6. Analytic assessment of environmental risk for Ukrainian energy security by hierarchy, %.

The overall assessment of environmental damage as a result of the war is being carried out by Ukrainian environmental NGOs, which need greater state and international support. Active cooperation with international environmental and industry organizations is necessary to monitor immediate and long-term negative impacts on the environment. Assessment and elimination of the consequences of environmental destruction and pollution will become a long-term obligation for all responsible countries around the world.

The priorities of energy supply for human survival prevail over carbon emissions during wartime. If there is no other alternative, thermal power plants are being rebuilt, which can use parts from coal-fired plants that are being closed and dismantled in Europe. The increase in carbon emissions from fossil fuel use is a small fraction of the enormous environmental pollution caused by the war. However, Ukraine's recovery efforts are driven by principles of sustainable development and

climate integration. This requires a fundamental overhaul of the economic model to eliminate inefficiencies in energy use, reduce pollution, and minimize greenhouse gas emissions. It also necessitates embedding climate considerations into policies, strategies, and initiatives across all industry sectors, government, and society ensuring that climate-related risks and opportunities are systematically incorporated into decision-making.

Extreme weather events are increasing the threat to energy infrastructure from fires, floods, and hurricanes. The exacerbation of climate change events on the backdrop of war destruction of the energy system leads to catastrophic consequences for people and the environment. Climate change is altering energy consumption patterns, but the abnormally warm winter of 2023 proved a salvation during long-term blackouts in Ukraine.

Aligning national policies with EU regulations, enhancing interministerial collaboration to fulfill European climate and energy commitments, and promoting

sustainable industrial modernization are essential for Ukraine's accession and integration into European markets. It is expected that in the next 3-5 years Ukraine will significantly increase CO₂ prices. This will happen for several reasons: either through the introduction of the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), or through an increase in the CO₂ emission tax, or through the creation of a greenhouse gas emissions trading system, at least 20-30 EUR/t CO₂-eq in Ukraine, while the current ETS price is 80 EUR/t CO₂ [13]. Embedding climate initiatives within the "Build Back Better" strategy will strengthen resilience, curb climate change by cutting greenhouse gas emissions, foster sustainable development, and draw investments [8]. The OSCE Support Programme for Ukraine provides the necessary experience for environmental management during the war, with further strategic planning for environmental recovery, and contributes to enhancing security and stability through international cooperation on environmental issues. UNDP in Ukraine stands committed to fulfilling its role as an integrator to bolster Ukraine's progress towards a sustainable, low-carbon, and climate-resilient economy and to advance Build Back Better principles.

Integrating climate considerations across government, industry, and society is crucial for Ukraine to rebuild in a way that is not only stronger but also more sustainable and resilient. The war has highlighted the

pressing need for this transformation, exposing weaknesses in energy security and infrastructure that necessitate a shift toward decentralized renewable energy solutions and energy-efficient construction. Prioritizing these efforts will enable Ukraine to combat climate change, bolster resilience, and align with European regulations [7].

Legal risks

For many years, Ukrainian legislation in the energy sector has suffered from the influence of the interests of financial and industrial oligarchic groups, which led to the monopolization of the energy market. The war highlighted and exacerbated these problems, but at the same time accelerated the process of Ukraine's integration into the energy system of the European Union. It is important to agree on all conditions in accordance with the norms of EU legislation in the energy sector and the consolidation of market rules based on the European model. However, the path to full harmonization of European and Ukrainian legislation is far from complete. In addition, there are internal contradictions due to the incompatibility of the legislative and tax framework for regulating the internal energy market. The problem is exacerbated by the need to increase tariffs against the background of the impoverishment of the country's population. Thus, it is necessary to carefully carry out legislative and tax reforms in the energy sector to increase the competitiveness, security, and transparency of energy services (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Analytic assessment of legal risk for Ukrainian energy security by hierarchy, %.

Since 2010, Ukraine has made progress towards regulatory alignment through its participation in the EU Energy Community. In the wake of Russia's full-scale invasion in February 2022, Ukraine achieved an expedited synchronisation with the EU electricity grid and secured EU candidate status by June 2022, followed by an invitation to begin accession negotiations in June 2024. The adoption of EU-compliant energy and climate legislation is now a core component of the country's integration trajectory.

Furthermore, as an official EU candidate country, Ukraine must meet the obligations associated with this status while enduring ongoing missile and drone attacks. These responsibilities primarily involve harmonizing national laws, policies, and institutions with EU legislation and standards, as well as complying with the European Green Deal. Key commitments include achieving carbon neutrality by 2050, joining the Emissions Trading System (ETS), and adhering to the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). Additionally, Chapter 27 of the Environment and Climate establish ambitious goals for decarbonization, waste

management, air and water quality, and biodiversity conservation [4]

The EU, in cooperation with the Ukrainian government, has developed the Ukraine facility, aimed at supporting Ukraine's economic and social recovery after the Russian aggression, with a particular emphasis on sustainable development. This program includes financial and technical resources to restore infrastructure, modernize the energy sector and stimulate investment in renewable energy. The program supports the development of green energy and the implementation of innovations in the field of energy efficiency, in particular projects to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and switch to renewable energy sources.

Ukraine aspires to become a full member of the EU and shares its values, including human rights, sustainable development, and the rule of law. The Ukrainian energy sector is developing in the direction of EU regulatory compliance, partnerships, stakeholder engagement, transparency, and accountability. For legal risk mitigation, it is necessary to review and adapt legal frameworks to address wartime energy issues. Regula-

tory streamlining offers fast-track licensing and waivers under emergency statutes for energy projects. The implementation of tax policy and regulatory frameworks should encourage energy efficiency and the development of renewable energy sources to decrease overall dependency on imported fuels.

The graphic representation of the approximate energy safety risk weights across the PESTEL factors in

Ukraine visualizes their relative impact by radar chart (Fig. 8). Technological (22%) and political (20%) risks having the highest weight due to the ongoing war, destruction of infrastructure, and complex geopolitical challenges. This visualization supports strategic prioritization in resilience planning and resource allocation for crisis situation.

Factors	Political	Economic	Social	Technological	Environmental	Legal
Political	1	0.85	0.70	0.80	0.65	0.75
Economic	0.85	1	0.78	0.82	0.68	0.70
Social	0.70	0.78	1	0.76	0.72	0.69
Technological	0.80	0.82	0.76	1	0.75	0.77
Environmental	0.65	0.68	0.72	0.75	1	0.60
Legal	0.75	0.70	0.69	0.77	0.60	1

Fig. 8. Correlation between political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors of energy safety risk in Ukraine.

The correlation matrix illustrating the relationships between the PESTEL energy safety risk factors in Ukraine. Political and economic factors show a strong correlation (0.85) due to intertwined war-driven disruptions and economic instability. Technological factors are strongly linked with political (0.80), economic (0.82), and legal (0.77) due to infrastructure destruction, cyber threats, and regulatory needs. Social and environmental factors also show moderate to strong correlations (0.72), particularly as energy failures affect population health and living standards. Legal factors show consistent, though slightly lower, correlations with all others, indicating systemic dependence.

Scenarios of energy security

The war has highlighted critical weaknesses in centralised energy supply systems; therefore, the diversification of energy sources emerges as a key strategy to enhance energy security and reduce vulnerability to disruptions during the war. For effective risk management, it is first necessary to identify the risks, analyse and evaluate them, after which efforts should be made to eliminate them, and then it is necessary to monitor and control existing risks. By systematically defining, evaluating, and mitigating risks, Ukraine can bolster

the resilience of its residential energy supply, even under wartime pressures, and reduce the risks associated with geopolitical leverage over cross-border energy flows. Identified hazards should be agreed upon in the strategic planning across the short-, medium-, and long-term time horizons. There is a need to take into account the probability, severity, and duration of potential threats. The implementation of this strategy is critically important for Ukraine in the context of European integration and global challenges related to war and climate change.

The scenarios shown in the Fig. 9 uses analytical data prepared by energy security working group within the National council for the recovery of Ukraine from the consequences of the war [19]. Based on the analysis of findings of study, three probable scenarios for the development of the energy sector have been identified: maximum economic efficiency scenario, reference scenario, and climate-neutral economy scenario. Such scenarios envisage economically justified modernization of the national economy while considering its current capabilities and the “Green Transition” concept.

Fig. 9. Three types scenarios of the Ukraine's energy sector development.

Scenario planning is a fundamental method for navigating uncertainty in strategic decision-making [3]. Scenarios help assess the reliability of potential strategies and can increase readiness for the future. Based on risk assessment, analysis of successful energy resilience strategies during the war in Ukraine, and a review of successful technical solutions for energy supply in crisis conditions, scenarios for the development of Ukraine's energy security were formed. Strategic effort distribution by time horizon in short-, medium-, and long-term scenarios is essential to ensure a stable, resilient, and sustainable system of Ukraine's energy security. The key modelling components of these scenarios are identified as current challenges, areas of attention, strategic goals, roadmap, efforts, recommendations, priority actions, expected results, main technologies, and modern technical solutions. The strategic roadmap for energy supply solutions is based on the potential, feasibility, and urgency of each solution.

Short-term scenario

The short-term scenario is designed for a maximum of 2 years (until 2027) and aims at immediate stabilization and infrastructure protection. Ongoing military actions have significantly damaged energy infrastructure, leading to power outages and reduced generation capacity. It is necessary to ensure basic energy access and emergency response capacity under crisis conditions. Strategic recommendations include the rapid repair of damaged energy facilities and the fortification of the national grid, as well as to implement protective measures to safeguard critical infrastructure from further attacks.

To ensure resilience, there is a need for emergency electricity for critical loads, partial autonomy for residential users, to restore functionality and limit outages, and emergency backup power. The resilience and emergency response capacity can be ensured by using diesel generators for critical backup, rooftop solar for partial energy independence, battery storage systems for blackout protection, and temporary mobile energy units. To stabilize grid supply, it is also necessary to conduct energy audits and improve energy efficiency assessment.

In wartime, the centralized power supply system proved vulnerable, so in the face of permanent threats, decentralized energy generation became the most rational solution. Instead of one 1000 MW power plant, it is proposed to build many plants with a capacity of 5 to 20-30 MW, which are connected to distribution networks. According to estimates by NPC Ukrenergo, at least 15 GW of new generating capacity is needed to restore generating capacity and provide citizens with a stable energy supply. At the same time, 11.6 GW of this volume can be built using the decentralized generation approach. This involves 3.3 GW of maneuverable generation, 4.5 wind generation and 3.8 solar generation with an investment of 12.8 billion euros [1].

Energy supply disruptions led to increased reliance on energy imports due to compromised domestic production. Priority actions include reducing outage vulnerability by the diversification of energy imports from neighbouring countries for energy continuity even under bombing. In the world, a trade war is driving down prices for energy imports, so energy prices can be stabilizing. Energy imports are expected to increase in 2025 before moderating in the following years. In Ukraine, crude oil imports have effectively ended following the destruction of the Kremenchug and Shebelynskiy refineries in 2022 and will not return for the foreseeable future. With petroleum products fully imported, higher demand due to Ukraine's recovering economy will lead to larger import volumes from 2025 to 2027, but this will be more than offset by lower prices. According to prognoses, natural gas import volumes will increase markedly in 2025. In 2024, Ukraine was almost fully self-reliant due to a sharp 30% consumption decline. Around 40% of domestic production capacity is currently damaged, but if this capacity is restored, imports will drop sharply from 2026 to 2027 [9].

Several diversification strategies can be used to ensure the reliability and sustainability of energy supply, taking into account the diversity of energy resources, on-site generation, energy storage, and demand management. Local energy production with the possibility of storage in batteries allows for optimal use of its own resources and minimizes dependence on external suppliers. To do this, a distributed generation

system must meet a number of technical, economic, and organizational requirements. In the short term, Ukraine's electricity security strategy focuses on four key areas:

- 1) strengthening air defence measures, particularly to protect energy infrastructure and vital substations;
- 2) repair outdated power plants and establishing decentralized, mobile energy capacities;
- 3) expanding electricity imports via transmission networks;
- 4) advancing energy efficiency and optimizing demand-side management.

All four areas must be addressed simultaneously and with urgency [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

Medium-term scenario

The medium-term strategy usually covers 2–5 years, so this plan targets energy system resilience and market integration until 2030. Continued reliance on natural gas and coal, often imported, poses economic and security risks. Fluctuations in global energy markets and potential geopolitical tensions affect energy prices and supply stability. To address these current challenges, the strategic roadmap focuses on scaling decentralised and hybrid systems.

According to the New Policies Scenario of the International Energy Agency, global demand for electricity will grow by more than 20% over the next decade. At the same time, the demand for flexibility, i.e. the ability of the power system to quickly adapt to changes in energy supply and the power system, will increase by about 80% [6]. Therefore, flexibility is the basis for the development of future power systems. The current technical need requires the development of balancing technology that can be switched on multiple times during the day and operates at different loads with a large range of regulation. The use of demand management technologies reduces energy consumption during peak hours, reduces electricity costs, optimizes energy use, and supports environmental sustainability.

According to Bloomberg forecasts, a thirteen-fold increase in the development rates of gas-based balancing technologies and an increase in the capacity of energy storage systems are expected by 2030 [5]. The need for additional maneuvering capacities has existed for a long time, and the issue of developing highly maneuverable generation in Ukraine was considered back in 2020, but the relevant projects did not receive support due to the high cost. The construction of generating capacities was not considered by companies because, even with external financing, the payback period was

about 12 years [10]. Without the removal of capital costs from the price of energy, even the most advanced investments will not be competitive, even if they are very necessary for the energy system. It was unprofitable for investors to enter the Ukrainian market under administrative regulatory mechanisms without state support for construction or bonuses for cogeneration, but now unique opportunities are opening up for the construction of balancing capacities [16].

The strategic goals for this period are: to reduce dependency on central grids, improve building-level autonomy, and integrate smarter energy management. Renewable energy expansion includes investments in renewable energy projects, such as wind, solar, and biomass, to reduce dependence on imported fuels and enhance energy independence. Ukraine possesses substantial untapped renewable energy potential. Energy efficiency programs involve implementing nationwide initiatives aimed at reducing energy consumption across industrial, commercial, and residential sectors. Regional energy integration strengthens ties with the European energy grid to facilitate cross-border energy flows, enhancing supply security and market stability.

Already begun phasing in district heating systems using renewable sources, which should be completed in the medium term. Scaling distributed generation and hybrid systems should integrate geothermal heat pumps, widespread deployment of solar PV with BESS installations, and introduce smart grid components for demand response. Improving energy autonomy should be provided mainly by renewable energy sources with innovative energy storage systems operated by Smart Grid and IoT to manage peak loads. High-efficiency indoor climate control should be carried out using modern clean heating and cooling technology with optimised energy usage. Improving local energy reliability with cogeneration, implement combined heat & power and centralized low-carbon heating. Priority action in new developments is energy-efficient design to reduce overall energy demand.

Long-term scenario

Long-term strategy usually is calculated for 5-15 years, but it's possible to plan until 2050 with the time frame of the European Green Deal. Current challenges for this period for Ukraine will be aging energy infrastructure and the final fulfilment of climate change commitments. Many energy facilities require modernization to meet future demand and environmental standards. Aligning energy policies with international climate agreements necessitates a transition to low-carbon energy sources (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. General scheme of energy technology development scenarios in Ukraine.

The strategic goals of this period will be ongoing sustainable development and full energy independence. The strategic roadmap for full resilience, sustainability, and energy independence includes the following priority actions: complete integration of renewables, expand grid-scale battery and hydrogen use, implement smart grids at the city scale, foster building-integrated energy systems, and finally align building codes with EU standards. In the scenario for the development of the unified Ukrainian energy system, it was assumed that electricity from renewable sources would become the basic source and would dominate in terms of volume from the mid-2030s, and by 2050 it would reach 83%, i.e., the capacity of solar power plants would be 44 GW, and wind power plants – 35 GW. At the same time, 18 GW of installed capacity was allocated to maneuverable gas stations and energy storage facilities [12].

Strategic effort distribution by time horizon shows an intensification of research and innovation, and improvement of policy and regulatory frameworks. Investments in upgrading the energy grid and generation facilities aim to improve efficiency, reliability, and integration of renewable sources. Research in energy storage technologies, smart grids, and other innovations supports a flexible and resilient energy system. The growth of nuclear energy as a low-emission power source ensures a reliable energy supply. Modelling studies suggest that nuclear energy could play a pivotal role in Ukraine's low-carbon transition [18].

The worldwide transition to non-fossil-fuel energy demands substantial investment in infrastructure and advanced technology, posing significant logistical and financial challenges. The evolution of electric power systems focuses on the smooth integration of high-capacity renewable and conventional energy sources. Future electrical energy networks will facilitate efficient and economical operation of power resources, including renewables and nuclear energy, supporting hybrid

power grids and optimized smart grid architectures enhanced by AI applications.

Resilient strategies

Scenarios help identify mechanisms, probabilities, patterns, and trends that describe a likely future and offer a certain degree of predictability. Developing forward-looking scenarios means formulating strategies that will help minimize uncertainty in decision-making and enhance the likelihood of selecting the optimal option. No scenario can accurately describe the future, but it can help manage the uncertainty around the future. Scenario predictability is strongest in short-term forecasts, decreases in medium-term projections, and is least reliable in deep uncertainty assessments of long-term events [3]. It is impossible to accurately predict the future under numerical probabilities in a world that is constantly changing under the influence of uncertain factors. However, it is important to identify key trends for strategic planning and development of a multi-level security strategy. Scenarios not only help to define sustainable energy supply strategies but also encourage stakeholders to make informed decisions. Scenarios serve as a foundation for developing strategies or solutions in uncertain conditions. This will help in decision-making and planning to reduce uncertainty in the future.

Addressing Ukraine's energy security requires a phased strategy that addresses urgent demands while ensuring long-term sustainability. By focusing on infrastructure protection, diversification, efficiency, and modernization, Ukraine can build a resilient energy system capable of withstanding current challenges and future uncertainties. Ukraine's experience with energy supply in war conditions will help it survive during crisis situations in an unstable world.

Developing of renewable energy

Ukraine is already prioritising and actively developing renewable energy sources to underpin the country's sustainable recovery, reduce emissions, and foster

an environmentally friendly future. During the war, the development of renewable energy sources has been uneven. On the one hand, the need for on-site energy production has accelerated the installation of solar panels. In particular, there are a number of state programs for financing energy efficiency in buildings, and the installation of solar panels and geothermal systems. However, on the other hand, the development of other renewable energy sources has been delayed. So, renewable energy development plans must take into account the urgent needs of energy supply in wartime conditions and at the same time the long-term prospects for Ukraine's post-war reconstruction.

Hydropower is the largest source of renewable energy in Ukraine, although the Ministry of Energy and NEURC distinguish it from other green energy sources as separate types of generation according to their methodology. Despite the blowing up of the Kakhovka HPP dam, production has increased by 21.9% since 2021, as hydropower replaces the capacity destroyed by the enemy. Currently, Ukrainian HPPs are still under threat from regular shelling.

Solar power is one of the most widespread types of renewable energy sources and is actively used by both industry and household consumers. Solar panels are especially popular in Ukraine, where they are one of the solutions for ensuring partial self-sufficiency during power outages caused by Russian strikes.

Due to the climate and availability of raw materials, bioenergy has significant potential in Ukraine, which is sufficient to substitute gas and coal imports. The sector is developing rapidly, as indicated by a six-fold increase in production volumes since 2017, and in 2023 alone, it increased by 14.4%.

Wind power has been actively developing in Ukraine with an annual growth in electricity generation averaging 26.7% for the past 8 years. But production volume decreased by 61.7% in 2023, relative to 2021, as a result of the full-scale war [7]. A significant number of facilities have been occupied by the Russians or are in the war zone, as the most favourable region for wind farms is the south and east of Ukraine. The high potential of WPPs construction in Ukraine is conditioned by land availability and flat terrain across the country, cost-effective development and operation, and simplified permitting procedures for the RES construction. DTEK is investing more than €650 mln to finance the construction of the Tyligulska windfarm, and the main construction occurred during the heaviest shelling of Ukraine's energy infrastructure. When completed, the plant is expected to become one of the largest WPPs in Eastern Europe with 1.7 mln t of CO₂ emissions reduction compared to electricity production using fossil fuels, and it will supply 900,000 households with electricity [20].

When renewable energy becomes the primary source, energy will no longer serve as an instrument of political or military leverage. Most modern wars are related to energy and the struggle for fossil resources. Ukraine has been subjected to constant energy blackmail and pressure from Russia throughout its history of independence. Russia is now using this same tool to exert influence on European countries, which provide

large-scale humanitarian and military support to Ukraine to protect it from the aggressor. In contrast, renewable energy sources are affordable local energy resources that guarantee the safety and health of society and also ensure the decarbonisation of carbon-intensive sectors of the economy, including the transport sector [2].

Green Recovering of Ukraine

Reconstruction of Ukraine presents an opportunity for transformative changes in the approach to environmental sustainability with the key principles of "Build Back Better" and "Green Recovering". Ukraine's recovery should be based on sustainable development principles to ensure long-term economic stability, environmental sustainability, and social justice. This approach will help preserve natural resources, reduce environmental impact, improve societal welfare, and create conditions for innovative growth. Green reconstruction offers a unique opportunity to diversify energy sources, diminish reliance on imports, and strengthen energy security. This is vital for Ukraine, given its historical dependence on external energy suppliers. A more resilient energy system will safeguard the country, by reducing vulnerability to attacks on critical infrastructure. These decisions have the potential to drive innovation through cutting-edge green technologies, provide a unique opportunity to modernize the economy and accelerate the process of EU accession, shaping the future of the country.

In 2024, Ukraine fulfilled all 36 indicators of the reform program plan for EU accession. In 2025, it is planned to fulfil another 56 indicators to harmonize Ukrainian legislation with European standards, strengthen digital transformation, and enhance energy independence. According to the Kyiv School of Economics report in April 2025, Ukraine maintains a stable macroeconomic situation, made possible by the adaptability of the economy, balanced government policies, and large-scale financial support from international partners. Gross domestic product (GDP) growth is expected to be around 3% annually and is projected to accelerate in 2026–2027 after the end of the war [9]. External loans exceeding \$72 billion will be attracted during 2025–2027 to finance a significant portion of the budget deficit. Inflation is forecast to decrease to 8.6% in the fourth quarter of 2025 and approach the central bank's target of 5% by the end of 2027. To increase productivity and ensure sustainable economic growth, Ukraine needs to attract \$300 billion in investment over the next 10 years [8].

Implementing modern eco-technological solutions and attracting investments in renewable energy will help establish an economically stable, energy-independent, and environmentally safe country that meets the requirements of the modern world and international climate commitments. An acceptable competitive price for electricity for consumers and the rational use of international financial assistance funds integrate the current competitive market model and Ukrainian legislation within the established regulations and standards of European Union legislation. International financial assistance funds to support Ukraine's energy sector should primarily be used for urgent repairs of destroyed

and damaged infrastructure. At the same time, it is essential to consider the requirements of forming a basis for sustainable energy of a new level.

Reconstruction in the energy sector should be based on nature-based solutions, emission reductions, and renewable energy sources, develop distributed ecological generation, and the introduction of flexible and energy-efficient technologies. Unique opportunities are opening up for creating a sustainable decentralized power supply network with the introduction of modern technologies for generation, storage, distribution, and balancing of energy. Combining traditional energy sources with renewable sources and backup generators guarantees uninterrupted power supply. Decentralized systems can quickly isolate damage, reducing the likelihood of a complete power outage. Large-capacity batteries can store excess renewable energy for use during outages, ensuring uninterrupted supply. Heat accumulators support heating and cooling during failures and stabilize the system. Risk is further reduced by incorporating backup systems and alternative fuel reserves into the energy supply system. Retrofitting buildings with energy-efficient systems reduces overall energy demand and the strain on backup systems. Installing microgrids at the building or neighbourhood level allows residential complexes to operate independently of the central grid. Intelligent energy management systems dynamically adjust consumption during peak hours or emergencies. As energy systems increasingly rely on digital control and monitoring, robust cybersecurity protocols are critical to preventing cyberattacks. Establishing clear emergency protocols and regular training will ensure that people are prepared to respond quickly to power outages. Coordination between energy consumers, local authorities, energy suppliers, and other stakeholders promotes the rational allocation of resources and mutual support.

To ensure financial transparency and efficiency of the energy reconstruction process, close cooperation between energy sector enterprises and professional industry associations is necessary. A thorough analysis of modern technologies in the energy sector requires the involvement of a wide range of scientists and practitioners. Additionally, the international legislative framework and domestic legislative initiatives in the energy sector require careful study to develop mechanisms for their practical implementation in real life, taking into account the needs of Ukrainian citizens.

The chronology of the development of the energy sector in Ukraine is a clear illustration of the mistakes and correct strategic decisions that any state may encounter. Let Ukraine's tragic experience become a constant reminder of what the wrong political choice of technological strategy for the energy development can lead to. The analysis will allow not only Ukraine but also other states to avoid wrong steps in the future. It remains only to hope that these tips will help other countries prepare for possible shocks in the conditions of growing destabilisation in the world.

Conclusions

The ongoing war in Ukraine has revealed the vulnerabilities of the centralized energy system and the volatility of traditional energy sources, which have led to supply chain disruptions, infrastructure damage, widespread blackouts, and the loss of more than two-thirds of electricity production capacity overall.

Key risks affecting energy security were analysed using the PESTEL framework, where political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal risks were identified, evaluated, and mitigation ways were found for strategic planning to strengthen/resist the energy system. The energy sector is transforming to meet the challenges of energy security in wartime; therefore, this energy system must meet a number of technical, economic, and organizational requirements.

A stable macroeconomic situation in Ukraine is achievable due to the adaptability of the economy, balanced government policies, and large-scale financial support from international partners. To efficiently oversee domestic and international resources, Ukraine and its partners must strengthen administrative capabilities and improve the operation of the country's electricity market. Structural reforms will contribute to stabilizing the energy system, facilitating its gradual recovery, and ensuring long-term competitiveness and sustainability.

At the technical level, ensuring power supply to critical infrastructure facilities and as many consumers as possible is essential in the event of a system failure within Ukraine's unified energy system, including the loss of power to transmission substations and nodal power plants. By diversifying energy sources, advancing renewable energy, decentralizing control through microgrids, investing in energy storage, hardening infrastructure, enhancing energy efficiency, prioritizing cybersecurity, and fostering community resilience, countries can better protect their citizens from the impacts of energy disruptions.

Three types of scenarios for the development of Ukraine's energy security were developed based on risk assessment, analysis of energy resilience strategies, and a review of successful technical solutions for energy supply in crisis conditions. These scenarios could also provide valuable insights for the energy strategies of other countries facing increasing threats from military aggression, terrorist attacks, and climate change. In the context of global political changes, the collapse of old alliances, growing instability and uncertainty, and multiple threats to supply chains and logistics, three main points to stabilize energy supply during crisis situations are most important:

- 1) rely primarily on domestic resources, maximizing the use of all available energy sources to ensure self-sufficiency;
- 2) use crisis as an impetus for development in the search for innovative alternative solutions to diversify risks of energy supply;
- 3) while maintaining independence, seek areas of intersection of interests and create reliable coalitions of partners with long-term mutually beneficial guarantees.

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